

Stereoselective synthesis of new coumarin and *N*-methylcarbazole retinoic acid analogs

Diana Ivanova^{a*}, Miglena Vassileva^b, Nikolaj Vassileva^b, Iva Pashkuleva^c and Rositza Koleva^c

^aInstitute de Genetique et de Biologie Moleculaire et Cellulaire, 67 404 Illkirch Cedex, Strasbourg, France

E-mail : diana@igbmc.u-strasbg.fr Fax : 33-3-88653201

^bInstitute of Organic Chemistry, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia 1113, Bulgaria

^cDepartment of Chemistry, University "St. Kliment Ochridsky", Sofia 1126, Bulgaria

Manuscript received 23 April 2002, revised 5 December 2002, accepted 17 December 2002

Some new coumarin and *N*-methylcarbazole derivatives of retinoic acid have been synthesized.

The retinoids are analogs of vitamin A, which is metabolized *in vivo* to retinoic acid, retinal, anhydroretinol, 14-hydroxy-4,14-retroretinol. The biological functions of vitamin A – cellular proliferation and differentiation, growth support, growth inhibition, embryogenesis, vision etc. – are mediated by a great diversity of retinoid binding proteins. *9-Cis* and *all trans*-retinoic acids are ligands of the retinoic acid receptors (RARs, RXRs), involved in the transcription of specific genes, regulating the processes of cellular proliferation and differentiation^{1, 2}. *All trans*-retinoic acid (Fig. 1) is successfully used in the therapy of acute promyelocytic leukemia, but prolonged application leads to resistance and retinoic acid syndrome³. New retinoic acid analogs are widely used in the research for new therapeutic substances, having improved pharmaceutical properties – decreased toxicity and optimized anticancer activity.

Fig. 1.

Recently, it has been established that chromane retinoids can activate specific retinoic acid receptors and have decreased toxicity⁴. Some coumarin derivatives possess also anticancer activity⁵. Structure-activity relationships of

coumarin retinoids will be object of future investigations in connection with the finding of the Chinese authors that some styrylcoumarin derivatives {*cis*-7-[(3-ethoxycarbonyl)-phenylethenyl]-4-methylcoumarin}⁶ have also anticancer properties.

In this work we report the synthesis of new coumarin and *N*-methylcarbazole derivatives of retinoic acid (1–5, Schemes 1 and 2). Compounds 1 and 2 are the first reported coumarin retinoic acid analogs having an isoprenoid side-chain and compound 4 is a new coumarin ethenyl-retinobenzoic acid.

The analogs 4 and 5, having a benzene ring in the side-chain, linked by an ethenyl fragment to the heterocyclic

Method A: (EtO)₂P(O)CH₂C(CH₃)=CH-COOCH₃, *t*-BuOK, 18-crown-6, CH₂Cl₂, r.t.
Method B: (EtO)₂P(O)CH₂C(CH₃)=CH-COOCH₃, NaH, THF, -30; -40°C

Scheme 1. Synthesis of retinoic acid analogs 1–3.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of arotinoids 4, 5.

moiety of the molecule, belong to the group of retinobenzoic acids, classified as polyaromatic retinoids (arotinoids). They are of interest as analogs of TTNPB {(*E*)-4-[2-(5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-5,5,8,8-tetramethyl-2-naphthalenyl)-1-propenyl]-benzoic acid, Fig. 1}, which has been found to be more effective in anticancer assays than retinoic acid and vitamin A, but has an increased toxicity.

The synthesis of the new retinoids is presented here as extension of our previous work on the retinoid synthesis⁷. Different bases [*n*-BuLi, NaH, LDA, NaOMe, *t*-BuOK, KN(TMS)₂, K₂CO₃, NaOH], solvents (THF, DMSO, CH₂Cl₂ etc.) and PTC catalysts (18-crown-6, 15-crown-5) have been used for the olefination reactions^{1,8,9}. β -Coumarinyl acrylates have been synthesized diastereoselectively using the Wittig and Wittig-Horner reagents¹⁰.

Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons (HWE) olefination method was employed for condensations of the corresponding heterocyclic aldehydes with C₅-phosphonate (Scheme 1) or methyl 4-[(diethylphosphono)methyl]benzoate (Scheme 2) under different sets of experimental conditions.

Phase transfer catalysis (PTC) conditions (Method A), using crown ethers as catalysts, were found to be most suitable for the synthesis of the coumarin analogs 1, 2 and 4. The condensation of the 6- or 7-formylcoumarins with phosphonates 6 and 7 (1.8 molar excess of the phosphonate) proceeded smoothly using potassium *tert*-butoxide in the presence of 18-crown-6 in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ under argon atmosphere. Nucleophiles (hydroxy, alkoxy anions) can attack the lactone cycle, giving products of nucleophilic addition or cause ring opening. In order to avoid isomerization of the intermediate *cis*- α -hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, obtained after ring opening of the coumarin lactone by treatment with strong bases; both the HWE-reaction and the basic hydrolysis (in 5 *N* NaOH/MeOH) were carried out

under dark conditions (dim red light). After acidification of the reaction mixture successful recyclization led to the desired coumarins 1, 2 and 4.

The HWE-condensations of the *N*-methylcarbazole-3-carbaldehyde¹¹ with the corresponding phosphonates for the synthesis of compounds 3 and 5 were carried out in two-stage procedure (Method B) using THF as a solvent and sodium hydride as a deprotonating agent. In this case the olefinations proceeded with complete conversion of the starting aldehyde without the use of PTC technique.

Subsequent hydrolysis of the esters, obtained after the HWE-reactions, furnished the desired compounds 1–5, having terminal carboxylic function.

The stereoselectivity of the olefination reaction and the stereostructure of the pure isomers, obtained as main products, were analyzed by 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopy. The olefination reactions proceeded with high *E*-stereoselectivity.

HWE-condensations of the coumarin- and *N*-methylcarbazole-3-carbaldehydes with C₅-phosphonate (Scheme 1) afforded the corresponding esters as an *E/Z* isomeric mixture of terminal double bond isomers with high stereoselectivity. The coupling constant values (*J* 15.9–16.1 Hz) for the vinyl hydrogens of the C4-C5 bond of the esters confirm the proposed *E*-configuration of the newly formed double bond. The presence of *ZZ,4E*-isomer (15–21%) after the olefination procedure is due to partial stereomutation of the conjugated C2-C3 double bond of the starting C₅-phosphonate in the presence of the deprotonating agent. The *2E,4E/2Z,4E* ratio of the esters obtained does not depend on the *E/Z* ratio of the C₅-phosphonate in the starting isomeric mixture.

The stereochemical analysis is important for elucidation of the biologically active configuration and conformation of the ligand in the binding site of the retinoic acid receptors. Two-dimensional Nuclear Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy (NOESY) was used for stereochemical analysis of the conformation of the final compounds having an isoprenoid side-chain. The interactions through the space observed between H-4 and H-2; and between H-5 and 3-CH₃ for compounds 2 and 3 were in agreement with the proposed *all E*-configuration of the side-chain. In the case of analog 2 irradiation of H-4 and H-5 gave NOEs on H-8' but the effect for H-4 was stronger. These interactions were in agreement with preferred *cisoid* conformation around the C5-C7' single bond in the molecule. Irradiation of H-4 in the case of analog 3 gave NOE on H-4' from the *N*-methylcarbazole heterocycle and is consistent with a preferred *cisoid* conformation around the C5-C3' single bond

between the cycle and the side-chain.

The interpretation of the preferred conformational structure of the cycle toward the side-chain for compound **1** is obscure because the interaction of H-4 and H-5 appears as a single peak for both the protons.

Only *E*-isomers obtained were stereospecific by the synthesis of the heteroarotinoids **4** and **5** (Scheme 2) as it was confirmed by the coupling constants values ($J_{\text{CH}=\text{CH}}$ 16.4–16.5 Hz) for the vinyl hydrogens in the ^1H NMR spectra of the esters in the crude reaction mixtures after the HWE-reaction. Basic hydrolysis of the esters in methanolic NaOH yielded the corresponding acids **4** and **5** without isomerization of the newly formed double bond ($J_{\text{CH}=\text{CH}}$ 16.4–16.6 Hz).

In summary, new analogs of retinoic acid and TTNPB were synthesized with high stereoselectivity. The reaction sequences involved HWE-reactions under different sets of experimental conditions followed by basic hydrolysis. Phase transfer catalysis was found to be the most effective method for the synthesis of coumarin retinoids. 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopy methods were used for determination of the stereoselectivity of the olefination reactions and for stereochemical analysis of the final products. The structures of **1–5** as individual stereoisomers were confirmed by spectral data and elemental analyses.

The new analogs **1–5** are useful probes in studies of the mechanism of the retinoid anticancer activity and in the search for retinoids activating specific isotypes of the retinoic acid receptors. The results from the biological experiments will be reported in near future.

Experimental

The coumarin retinoids 1, 2 and 4 using PTC. Method A : To a suspension of 6- or 7-formylcoumarin (1.4 mmol) in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 , was added the corresponding phosphonate {(methyl 4-(diethylphosphono)-3-methyl-2-butenate or methyl 4-[(diethylphosphono)methyl]benzoate} (2.52 mmol), dissolved in dry CH_2Cl_2 . Then *t*-BuOK (3.92 mmol) and cat. amount (1 mg) of 18-crown-6 were added in dark (dim red light) under argon atmosphere. The suspension was stirred (2 h) and left overnight in dark. After acidification (dil. HCl, 1 : 1) to pH 1–2, water was added, then the organic products were extracted (CH_2Cl_2), washed (H_2O) to neutral pH and the solvents were evaporated *in vacuo*.

The N-methylcarbazole retinoids 3 and 5. Method B : The solution of the corresponding phosphonate {(methyl 4-(diethylphosphono)-3-methyl-2-butenate or methyl 4-[(diethylphosphono)methyl]benzoate} (1.68 mmol) in an-

hydrous THF was added at –30 and –40° under argon atmosphere to a suspension of sodium hydride (3.82 mmol) in anhydrous THF and the suspension was stirred for 1 h. Then *N*-methylcarbazole-3-carbaldehyde (1.4 mmol) in anhydrous THF was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at –30 and –40° (1 h) and left for overnight under argon atmosphere at RT. Satd. NH_4Cl was then added, the organic layer extracted (EtOAc), washed (H_2O) to neutral pH and the solvents were evaporated *in vacuo*.

Hydrolysis of the esters : The product, obtained after the olefination procedure, was suspended in MeOH (150 ml), 5 *N* NaOH (75.5 ml) added (for the coumarin esters in dark conditions) and the reaction mixture was refluxed (4 h). After cooling, it was acidified (dil. HCl, 1 : 1) to pH 1–2 and diluted (1 : 1) with water. The product was isolated by extraction and crystallization from EtOAc.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported from Bulgarian National Council for Scientific Research (Pr. X-503). The authors thank Ms. Mladenova for practical advice at the early stage of this work.

References

1. "The Retinoids : Biology, Chemistry and Medicine", 2nd. ed., eds. M. B. Sporn, A. B. Roberts and D. S. Goodman, Raven Press, New York, 1994; "Chemistry and Biology of Synthetic Retinoids", eds. M. I. Dawson and W. H. Okamura, CRC Press, New York, 1990.
2. V. Giguere, E. S. Ong, P. Segui and R. M. Evans, *Nature*, 1987, **330**, 624; D. J. Mangelsdorf, U. Borgmeyer, R. A. Heyman, J. Y. Zhou, E. S. Ong, A. E. Oro, A. Kakizuka and R. M. Evans, *Genes Dev.*, 1992, **6**, 329.
3. M. F. Huang, Y. C. Ye, J. R. Chen, J. X. Lu, L. Zhao, L. J. Gu and Z. Y. Wang, *Blood*, 1988, **72**, 567; L. Altucci and H. Gronemeyer, *Nature Rev. Cancer*, 2001, **2**, 181.
4. M. I. Dawson, P. D. Hobbs, K. Derdzinski, R. L. S. Chan, J. Gruber, W. Chao, S. Smith, R. W. Thies and L. J. Schiff, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1984, **27**, 1516; D. M. Benbrook, Sh. Subramanian, J. B. Gale, S. Liu, C. W. Brown, M. F. Boehm and K. D. Berlin, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 3753.
5. R. V. Nair, E. P. Fischer, S. H. Safe, C. Cortez, R. G. Harvey and j. DiGiovanni, *Carcinogenesis*, 1991, **12**, 65.
6. Xu Song, Xu Shipping and Li Lanmin, *Yaoxue Xuebao*, 2000, **35**, 103 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **133**, 104942).
7. D. Ivanova, V. Kolev, Tz. Lazarova and E. Padros, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 2645; D. Ivanova, C. Gaudon, A. Rossin, W. Bourguet and H. Gronemeyer, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* 2002, **10**, 2099.
8. R. Baker and R. J. Sims, *Synthesis*, 1981, 117; M. I. Dawson,

Note

- K. Derdzinski, P. D. Hobbs, R. L.-S. Chan, S. W. Rhee and D. Yasuda, *J Org Chem* . 1984, **49**, 5265.
9. M. Blanchard-Desce, V. Alain, P. V. Bedworth, S. R. Marder, A. Fort, C. Runser, M. Barzoukas, S. Lebus and R. Wortmann, *Chem Eur J* . 1997, **3**, 1091, V. Alain, S. Rédoglia, M. Blanchard-Desce, S. Lebus, K. Lukaszuk, R. Wortmann, U. Gubler, C. Bosshard and P. Gunter, *Chem Phys* . 1999, **245**, 51; M. Mladenova, L. Ventelon and M. Blanchard-Desce, *Tetrahedron Lett* 1999, **40**, 6923.
10. L. N. Dutta and P. K. De, *J Indian Chem Soc* 1998, **75**, 684
11. N. Buu-Hoi and N. Hoan, *J Am Chem Soc* 1951, **73**, 98